

Five years of Ugly Architecture

(press release)

The Ugly Architecture community (in the Czech language *Ošklivá architektura*), united around the Facebook group *Ošklivá architektura*, celebrated five years of its existence this year. During that time, thousands of posts related to post-war architecture appeared in it. The group was founded at the beginning of 2018 by Jan Lochman as a reaction to the intention to demolish the Transgas complex in Prague. The community aims to promote the architecture of this period by involving the general public in its discovery and appreciation. In practice, it looks like the members of the group take photos of interesting post-war buildings, upload the photos to the group, and discuss them. That's why the name *Ugly* was also chosen. The goal was not to bring together a group of enthusiasts for this architectural period (for them, of course, this architecture is beautiful), but to create a discussion platform for everyone – that is, for those who consider this architecture to be worthless, ugly or communist and support its demolition.

After five years of existence, the wider public is thus involved in searching and discussing architecture – the group currently has slightly over 13,000 members. Most of them are from the Czech Republic, namely from Prague and Brno, but there are also participants from abroad. Although the group's goal is to discover mainly buildings realized in the territory of today's Czech Republic, buildings from the rest of the world also appear here. In addition to architecture, the group is interested in art in architecture and design.

In addition, the administrators of the group organize comment walks and lectures and maintain a Map of Endangered Architecture – that is, buildings that are threatened with demolition or drastic reconstruction. Since art is relatively easy to protect, it is occasionally pursued by members. The founder of the group saved several works of art and created a Database of Art in Architecture that contains over 16,000 items.

It is easier for individuals and small groups to protect art in architecture and small architectural artifacts than entire structures. Most of the buildings from this period are still irretrievably destroyed, although the first signs of change are appearing, such as the reconstruction of the former

Hotel Intercontinental in Prague or the repair of the funeral hall in Židenice in Brno. Therefore, the group will also try to grow in the future and will add other activities, such as award prizes for the promotion of post-war architecture, and will also publish its publication.

Glossary

Art in architecture – the term *art in architecture* means art that was compulsorily paid for from the budgets of buildings and urban planning units after the Second World War. From the sixties to the eighties of the 20th century, each investor had to release one to four percent of the budget for art, which subsequently decorated the given object. The decoration of the buildings was based on competitions or the opinions of expert committees. However, the state dictated the decoration of public space already in the 1950s.

Funeral Hall in Židenice – also known as *Židenice Funeral Hall* or *Ruller's Funeral Hall*; is a building in Židenice, part of Brno, the Czech Republic. It was designed by Ivan Ruller in the Scandinavian style in the late 1970s. The hall was used for funeral services until 2006 when it was closed due to poor condition. Since then, its deterioration has accelerated and some works of art have disappeared. This year, however, the city district of Brno-Židenice proceeded with the reconstruction, found the original works of art, and began to restore them.

Hotel Intercontinental – is a designation for a building located in the Prague city center. It began to be built at the end of the 1960s and its authors were Karel Filsak, Karel Bubeníček, and Jaroslav Švec. It served as a hotel until 2021 when the new owner began a complete renovation that continues to this day. Its goal, according to the owner, is to restore this brutalist building to its original form and thus rid it of non-original deposits that it has acquired over time.

Jan Lochman – founder of the Ugly Architecture group; for many years he has been active in the field of architecture, tourism, and photographic documentation, establishing documentation projects. A graduate of the Czech University of Life Sciences Prague, he studied information science at the Faculty of Arts of Charles University.

Map of Endangered Architecture – it mainly contains buildings about which there are some mentions that they will be demolished. Objects are classified into three categories: **demolition** (in Czech *demolice*) – where demolition is already underway; **critically endangered** (*kriticky ohroženo*) – where demolition will take place soon; and **threatened** (*ohroženo*) – where there are any reports of intended demolition. The map is updated once every six months and is available on Google Maps.

Ugly Architecture ([Ošklivá architektura](#)) – a group on the social network Facebook founded at the beginning of 2018 to promote the architecture of the second half of the 20th century in the Czech Republic. Members take photos of interesting buildings, share photos in the group, and discuss them.

Transgas complex – a demolished complex of buildings that stood on Prague's Vinohradská Street, not far from the National Museum building. It was built in the 1970s for the needs of the Transgas gas pipeline dispatch center and the Ministry of Fuel and Energy. It was designed by architects Jiří Eisenreich, Jindřich Malátek, Václav Aulický and Ivo Loos. The construction with elements of brutalism and high-tech architecture had its supporters among experts and the public. It was proposed to be registered in the list of cultural monuments, but in the end, it did not become a monument. Between 2019 and 2020, demolition was underway to build new houses on the site, but this has not happened so far and the plot is empty.